

The Influence of Fair Presentation and Audit Judgment on Audit Opinion Issuance by Public Accountants in Indonesia

Yulita¹, Grahita Chandrarin², Edi Subiyantoro³

^{1,2,3}University of Merdeka Malang

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
13 February 2026

Corresponding Author:
Yulita

ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the influence of fair presentation and audit judgment on the issuance of audit opinions in Public Accounting Firms (KAP) in Indonesia, with auditor experience as a moderating variable. The study uses a quantitative, causal design. Data were collected through questionnaires distributed to auditors at registered and licensed KAPs in Indonesia, using a purposive sampling technique. Data analysis was performed using Moderating Regression Analysis (MRA) in IBM SPSS Statistics version 27. The results show that fair presentation has a significant effect on the issuance of audit opinions, indicating that the presentation of fair, complete, accurate, and bias-free financial statements is a significant factor in forming auditor confidence in the fairness of financial statements. Conversely, audit judgment does not have a significant effect on the issuance of audit opinions, suggesting that the auditor's professional judgment in this study is not the main determining factor in the opinion. This finding indicates that the issuance of audit opinions is more strongly influenced by compliance with audit standards, the sufficiency of audit evidence, and the quality of financial statement presentation than by the auditor's subjectivity. This research provides theoretical contributions to the development of auditing literature, particularly regarding the role of fair presentation and the limited influence of audit judgment in the audit opinion-giving process, as well as practical implications for KAP in improving audit quality and the credibility of auditor opinions.

KEYWORDS: fair presentation, audit judgment, auditor experience, audit opinion, Public Accounting Firm.

1. INTRODUCTION

Audits are crucial for ensuring the transparency and reliability of a company's financial reports, as they play a vital role in the quality of its financial statements. Violations of audit postulates, such as materiality, economic substance, prudence, completeness, and consistency, can undermine the reliability of a company's financial reports and erode stakeholders' trust, including investors, creditors, and related parties (Boedihardjo & Ardini, 2024).

The auditor's role in providing an opinion on financial statements is crucial. Auditors are responsible for assessing a company's financial statements and providing an opinion on their fairness. An audit opinion is an opinion on the fairness of the presentation of the company's financial statements. Auditors must exercise professional skepticism to determine the accuracy and veracity of the evidence and information provided by the client (Jesika, 2015).

Auditors form an audit opinion as the final result of the audit process, which assesses the fairness and accuracy of an entity's financial statements. The audit process involves

the auditor's professional assessment of financial information, taking into account a thorough understanding of the audited entity's business and environment. The auditor forms this opinion based on compliance with applicable auditing standards and professional practice regulations.

One example of an audit opinion case is the Supreme Audit Agency (BPK) audit of government performance in the first semester of 2023. The report submitted to President Joko Widodo showed that 80 of the 81 ministries and institutions received an unqualified opinion (WTP), indicating that their financial reports were deemed in accordance with accounting principles and trustworthy. However, one ministry, the Ministry of Communication and Informatics (Kemenkominfo), received a qualified opinion (WDP) (Yanwardhana, 2023).

The reason for granting the WDP opinion was that the Supreme Audit Agency (BPK) findings exceeded established risk management standards, leading the Ministry of Communication and Informatics' activities to fail to align with planned programs. One significant finding concerned

the corruption case involving the Bakti Kominfo Base Transceiver Station (BTS). This finding was deemed material, exceeding the established risk threshold, thus influencing the BPK's assessment of the Ministry of Communication and Informatics' performance (Yanwardhana, 2023).

Financial statements must fairly present the company's financial position, financial performance, changes in equity, and cash flows by correctly applying accounting standards and providing the required disclosures in the notes to the financial statements. Other information is still disclosed to ensure a fair presentation, even if such disclosure is not required by the Statement of Financial Accounting Standards (Suhendar, 2020: 7).

The concept of fair presentation in financial statements plays a crucial role in guiding auditors to issue an audit opinion that reflects the audited entity's accurate and fair financial condition. Under IFRS standards and European Union directives, fair presentation encompasses faithful representation of transactions, events, and conditions. If compliance with applicable standards is deemed misleading to readers, the accurate and fair view or fair presentation principle allows overriding specific provisions (true and fair override) to present more accurate information (Garvey, 2021).

One case in Indonesia relevant to fair presentation is the manipulation of PT Garuda Indonesia (Persero) Tbk's financial statements in 2018. Garuda Indonesia's financial statements recorded revenue of IDR 2.9 trillion from a collaboration with PT Mahata Aero Teknologi to install Wi-Fi services on aircraft. This revenue was recognized even though payment had not yet been received, which is contrary to Financial Accounting Standards Principles (PSAK) 23 on Revenue (Friana, 2019).

Garuda Indonesia's commissioners refused to sign the financial statements, believing that the revenue recording did not comply with applicable accounting standards. They argued that revenue recognition should occur after payment is received or when payment is sure to be received. However, the majority of directors still approved the financial statements, and independent auditors from the Public Accounting Firm (KAP) Tanubrata, Sutanto, Fahmi, Bambang & Rekan issued an unqualified opinion (WTP) on the financial statements (Friana, 2019).

This case attracted the attention of the Financial Services Authority (OJK) and the Ministry of Finance. After an investigation, it was determined that the revenue recognition did not align with the substance of the transaction or applicable accounting standards. Consequently, the Ministry of Finance imposed sanctions on the independent auditor, including a 12-month suspension of its license for failing to comply with applicable auditing standards. Furthermore, Garuda Indonesia was required to restate its

2018 financial statements and was fined by the OJK (Friana, 2019).

Audit judgment is the auditor's consideration in determining an opinion regarding the results of his audit, which refers to the formation of an idea, opinion, or estimate about an object, event, status, or other type of event (Knapp, 1985). Brown (2014: 8) states that "audit judgment will direct the auditor to focus on making his best professional judgment." Audit judgment is the decision-making process by which the auditor determines an opinion on the fairness of an entity's financial statements.

This assessment involves interpreting data, understanding accounting principles, and evaluating existing risks. Providing an audit opinion makes audit judgment a key factor, as the auditor must critically and independently evaluate the existing audit evidence. Auditor decisions regarding audit judgment are strongly influenced by experience and expertise in identifying material misstatements and evaluating accounting policies (Anwar, 2018). Based on the problem formulation, the objectives of this study are to analyze the influence of fair presentation on the provision of the audit opinion and the influence of audit judgment on the provision of the audit opinion.

The theoretical benefit of this research is to contribute to the development of accounting science, particularly by advancing understanding of the influence of fair presentation and audit judgment on the provision of audit opinions, and by clarifying how audit experience, as a moderating variable, can strengthen or weaken the influence of these two factors.

The practical benefits of this research will contribute to several parties, including: This research provides an opportunity for researchers to deepen their understanding of the influence of factors such as fair presentation and audit judgment in the context of providing audit opinions, so that they can enrich their knowledge and analytical skills in assessing critical aspects that influence audit quality.

Public accounting firms can use this research as a practical guide to improve the accuracy of audit judgment and strengthen fair presentation assessment procedures, ultimately helping ensure the accuracy and reliability of audit opinions provided to clients.

This research helps increase awareness of the importance of presenting fair and accurate financial reports and of how auditors' judgments can influence the opinions they receive, thereby motivating companies to maintain the quality of their financial reports.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This research uses agency theory, a branch of game theory that studies the design of contracts to motivate a rational agent to act on behalf of a principal when the agent's interests would otherwise conflict with the principal's interests. Agency theory contracts have characteristics of

cooperative and non-cooperative games. Non-cooperation means that both parties choose to act independently. Neither party agrees explicitly to take a particular action; instead, these actions are motivated by the contract itself (Scott, 2015, p. 358).

Auditing is a systematic process of objectively obtaining and evaluating evidence related to assertions about economic actions and events to measure the degree of correspondence between those assertions and established criteria, and then communicating the results to interested parties (Boynton, 2001). Auditing is the accumulation and evaluation of evidence about information to determine and report on the degree of correspondence between the information and established criteria. Audits must be conducted by competent and independent individuals (Arens, 2017).

Auditing is a systematic process of obtaining and evaluating evidence related to assertions about economic actions and events, objectively determining the level of compliance with established criteria, and communicating the results to interested parties (Jusup, 2014).

The benchmarks for financial statement presentation performance are fair and unfair, not right or wrong. Fair is defined as acceptable by common sense, with a tolerance range. Correct, on the other hand, is something that must be the same, with an absolute value. Presenting financial statements with the correct benchmark cannot be achieved; it can only be used in the application of standards (Suhendar, 2020: 7).

Audit judgment is the auditor's consideration in determining an opinion regarding the results of his audit, which refers to the formation of an idea, opinion, or estimate about an object, event, status, or other type of event (Knapp, 1985). Brown (2014: 8) states that "audit judgment will direct the auditor to focus on making his best professional judgment".

Siregar (2019: 11) states that "the word judgment means the ability to make sensible decisions after carefully considering the best things to do regarding the core values of auditing such as integrity, independence, objectivity, confidentiality, code of ethics and professionalism". Judgment carried out by auditors involves the ability to be based on sound thinking and based on facts in the field in making decisions, carefully considering the things that are found in the audit, encompassing the core values of auditing, namely integrity, independence, objectivity, confidentiality, code of ethics and professionalism so that the resulting judgment is in accordance with the code of ethics and correct audit procedures, and also audit judgment is very dependent on perceptions of the situation.

Bouman & Bradley (1997: 93) state that experience is defined as the length of time spent working in a field, specifically the length of time spent on a job. People with

many audit assignments in their work will have more experience than those with only a few.

Audit experience is the auditor's experience in auditing financial statements, including the length of service and the number of assignments and reviews of similar issues (Masrizal, 2010). Sularso & Naim (1999) found that experienced auditors made better judgments in professional tasks than inexperienced auditors. The auditor's audit experience also plays a role in determining the considerations taken (Haynes, 1998).

3. METHOD

3.1 Research Design

The research design used was a causal, quantitative approach. Causality research design is a research design used to test the influence, relationship, or impact of independent variables on dependent variables (Chandrarin, 2017, p. 98).

3.2 Population and Sample

According to Chandrarin (2017: 125), a population is a collection of elements with specific characteristics that can be used to conclude. These elements can be people, managers, auditors, companies, events, or anything else of interest to observe or research. The population in this study comprises Public Accounting Firms (KAPs) across Indonesia.

According to Chandrarin (2017: 125), a sample is a collection of subjects that represent a population. The sample must have the same characteristics as the population and be representative of the population. The sampling technique used is purposive sampling. According to Chandrarin (2017: 126), purposive sampling is a sampling method based on specific criteria. The Public Accounting Firm (KAP) is selected based on specific criteria relevant to the research, including registered and licensed Public Accounting Firms (KAPs) and reputable Public Accounting Firms (KAPs).

3.3 Research Location

This research was conducted at various Public Accounting Firms (KAP) across Indonesia, representing diverse geographic and operational backgrounds. This location selection aimed to obtain a comprehensive picture of audit practices and the dynamics of auditor professionalism in a national context. With its broad scope, this research is expected to shed more light on the role of audit experience in strengthening fair presentation and audit judgment across a variety of real-world situations.

3.4 Data Analysis Techniques

This study uses moderated regression analysis in the IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27. This is an analysis technique that aims to test the strength or weakness of the relationship between independent and dependent variables (Chandrarin, 2017, p. 135; Harjono et al., 2024).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Result

4.1.1 Reliability Test

The reliability test describes the results of the research instrument's reliability testing to ensure the consistency and stability of the measuring instrument used for the variables of fair presentation, audit judgment, audit experience, and audit opinion. The reliability test in this study used Cronbach's alpha, with an alpha value of >0.60 as the criterion for declaring the research instrument reliable.

Table 1. Results of Reliability Test Calculation

Variables	Cronbach's	Standard	Information
Fair Presentation	0.895	0.60	Reliable
Audit Judgment	0.930	0.60	Reliable
Issuance of Audit Opinion	0.930	0.60	Reliable

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Table 1 shows that Cronbach's Alpha for all research variables exceeds the established standard (0.60), indicating that all research instruments are reliable and consistently used to measure the variables.

Descriptive statistics aim to explain the characteristics of the research data, including the mean, standard deviation, variance, minimum, and maximum values of the variables fair presentation, audit judgment, auditor experience, and audit opinion. This test provides a general overview of the distribution of data and the variability of respondents' responses in the study.

The financial statements presented include all relevant information for user decision-making (3.48). This is reinforced by the finding that all transactions during the accounting period have been fully recorded and reported (3.51). These two aspects emphasize the importance of audit experience in ensuring the completeness and relevance of information used as the basis for economic decisions.

Furthermore, the financial statements were prepared without bias in favor of any particular party (3.51), thus reflecting the auditor's objectivity in maintaining the integrity of the presentation. The financial information was also presented accurately in accordance with applicable accounting standards (3.61), demonstrating consistent application of professional principles. Therefore, the Public Accounting Firm (KAP) needs to continuously evaluate audit practices to ensure that relevance, completeness, objectivity, and accuracy remain top priorities in strengthening fair presentation and audit judgment.

A heteroscedasticity test was conducted to ensure that the moderated regression model did not differ in residual variance between observations. This study used the Glejser

test, which was based on a significance value of the independent variable greater than 0.05, indicating the absence of heteroscedasticity in the data.

Shows that the significance value of each independent variable, namely fair presentation (0.681), audit judgment (0.938), is all greater than 0.05, so it can be concluded that the moderated regression model is free from heteroscedasticity problems.

4.1.2 Moderating Regression Analysis (MRA) Test

Regression Analysis (MRA) was used in this study to determine whether audit experience strengthens or weakens the influence of fair presentation and audit judgment on the issuance of audit opinions. This test analyzes the interaction between the independent and moderator variables to identify significant changes in the relationship under investigation.

Table 2. Results of Regression Analysis (MRA) Test Calculations

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	-27,341	12,530		-2,182	.031
Fair Presentation	2,014	.577	1,943	3,489	<,001
Audit Judgment	.270	.496	.273	.545	.587

Source: SPSS Output (2025)

A fair presentation of the audit opinion shows a significant influence (Sig. = 0.001), so it can be concluded that fair presentation has a significant influence on the issuance of an audit opinion. Therefore, hypothesis H1 is accepted.

The audit judgment on the issuance of an audit opinion has no significant effect (Sig. = 0.587), so it can be concluded that audit judgment has no significant effect on the issuance of an audit opinion in this model. Therefore, hypothesis H2 is rejected.

4.2 Discussion

The research results show that fair presentation influences the issuance of an audit opinion. This demonstrates that presenting financial statements fairly and in accordance with generally accepted accounting principles is crucial to establishing auditor confidence in their fairness, thereby encouraging the issuance of an appropriate audit opinion.

Financial statements that include all relevant information are the primary foundation for supporting

informed decision-making by users. When information is presented comprehensively, auditors have a strong basis for assessing the fairness of the statements' presentation. This strengthens the auditor's confidence in issuing an opinion that reflects the audited entity's actual condition.

Complete recording and reporting of transactions demonstrates the integrity of an entity's accounting processes. This completeness facilitates the auditor's ability to trace and verify transactions. This allows the auditor to form an audit opinion based on complete and reliable evidence.

The preparation of unbiased financial statements reflects an entity's commitment to the principles of fairness and transparency. When there is no bias toward any particular party, the auditor can assess the statements objectively without considering potential conflicts of interest. This condition supports the provision of a neutral audit opinion in accordance with professional standards.

Accurate presentation of financial information in accordance with accounting standards demonstrates an entity's compliance with applicable regulations. This accuracy indicates that the financial statements can be trusted as an accurate representation of the financial condition. Auditors who find the presentation accurate will more easily reach a sound and convincing opinion.

Gathering sufficient audit evidence is a crucial step in the auditor's assessment of the financial statements. Sufficient evidence enables the auditor to assess whether the presentation of the statements meets the principle of fair presentation. With a strong evidence base, the auditor can issue an opinion that reflects a high degree of confidence in the fairness of the statements.

Performing adequate audit procedures demonstrates that the auditor has carried out their responsibilities thoroughly and professionally. These procedures include testing transactions, internal controls, and financial statement analysis. When procedures are performed adequately, the opinion rendered will be sound and accountable.

An audit report that objectively reflects the audit results demonstrates that external interests do not influence the auditor. This objectivity is essential to ensure that the opinion rendered accurately reflects the entity's financial condition. When the auditor is neutral and bases their opinion on evidence, the resulting opinion is more credible to reporting users.

The link between fair presentation and the audit opinion is clear when financial statements are prepared in full, accurately, and without bias. This allows the auditor to perform thorough audit procedures and gather sufficient evidence. Thus, fair presentation is the primary foundation for forming an objective and reliable audit opinion.

When an entity presents financial statements in accordance with accounting standards and reflects the actual conditions, the auditor has greater confidence in issuing an opinion. The quality of the financial statements presented

significantly influences the auditor's objectivity in preparing the audit report. Therefore, fair presentation not only impacts the audit process but also strengthens the quality and credibility of the resulting opinion.

Fair presentation refers to the presentation of financial statements that faithfully reflect the entity's economic condition and conform to generally accepted accounting principles. In the context of auditing, fair presentation is a key indicator for auditors in assessing management integrity and transparency. When financial statements are fairly presented, auditors have a strong basis for objectively evaluating the appropriateness of their opinion.

Auditors rely on professional skepticism and judgment to assess whether financial statements are fairly presented. When the elements of fair presentation are met, auditors tend to experience a reduced perceived risk of potential misstatement. Thus, fair presentation not only serves a technical function but also influences the auditor's cognitive process in forming an opinion.

International auditing standards, such as ISA 700, emphasize the importance of fair presentation as the basis for issuing an audit opinion. Auditors are required to assess whether the financial statements have been prepared in accordance with the applicable financial reporting framework, including aspects of the relevance and reliability of the information. When fair presentation is met, auditors have a normative basis to assert that the financial statements fairly present the entity's financial position and performance.

For Public Accounting Firms (KAP), understanding fair presentation is crucial to maintaining audit quality and professional reputation. Auditors who can accurately identify and assess fair presentation will be more consistent in providing opinions that reflect the entity's actual condition. Therefore, fair presentation is not merely a technical variable but also an ethical and professional foundation of the audit process.

These findings align with DeFond's (2018) research, which emphasized that the principle of fair presentation is more important than mere technical compliance with accounting standards. DeFond demonstrated that compliance without honest presentation can actually mislead report users, and that implementing fair presentation can reduce the risk of an audit opinion that does not reflect the company's actual economic condition.

Nwaobia's (2016) research also supports these findings by stating that the latest audit reporting standards, including ISA 701, can narrow the audit expectation gap through transparency of presentation and emphasis on auditor responsibility. This suggests that improving the quality of information presented in audit reports increases user confidence and influences perceptions of the opinion issued.

Similarly, Garvey (2021) found that fair presentation is closely related to auditors' professional judgment in

complex reporting situations. Although auditors tend to avoid using the "true and fair override," this attitude reflects a preference for presenting reports that reflect the proper conditions, ultimately strengthening the integrity of the audit opinion.

Meanwhile, a study by Shalimova (2016) explains that qualitative characteristics in auditor reports, such as objectivity, completeness, and clarity, are important aspects of fair presentation that support a credible audit opinion. When reports are prepared with these aspects in mind, auditors tend to provide more convincing and acceptable opinions to stakeholders.

Ibhadode (2020) also highlighted the importance of the accurate and fair view principle as an ethical representation in financial statements. When applied correctly, it can strengthen the auditor's justification for issuing an audit opinion. This demonstrates that the audit opinion is based not only on technical aspects but also on the consistency of the report's substance with the economic reality presented fairly.

Chukwu's (2019) findings reinforce the need for fair presentation to be supported by sufficient, appropriate, relevant, and reliable audit evidence. When the auditor obtains sufficient evidence to conclude that the statements are fairly presented, the opinion issued is likely to be accurate and accountable.

The results of the study indicate that audit judgment does not affect the issuance of an audit opinion. This indicates that the auditor's professional judgment in this model does not directly influence the final decision in issuing an audit opinion.

Considering time and resource efficiency in determining audit procedures demonstrates the auditor's awareness of the operational aspects of conducting an audit. While efficiency is crucial for a smooth process, it does not necessarily impact the quality of the opinion rendered. Efficiency plays a greater role in managing the audit process than in determining the final opinion.

The auditor's efforts to ensure sufficient evidence is gathered to support the opinion reflect a commitment to completeness. However, the completeness of the evidence does not necessarily guarantee that the judgment will directly influence the audit opinion. This demonstrates that even when judgment is exercised carefully, the opinion remains dependent on established standards and procedures.

Alignment between audit procedures and audit objectives indicates that the auditor is working systematically and purposefully. Even if the procedures performed align with the objectives, the judgments made are not always the primary determinant in issuing an opinion. This confirms that objective examination results have a greater influence on the audit opinion than the auditor's subjective judgment.

Gathering sufficient audit evidence is a crucial foundation for developing a reliable opinion. Auditors who

focus on evidence tend to produce opinions that are more objective and reflect the entity's actual conditions. This indicates that the strength of the evidence more influences the opinion than personal judgment.

Performing adequate audit procedures demonstrates that the auditor adheres to professional standards in carrying out their duties. Adequate procedures ensure that the opinion rendered is well-founded. Thus, the audit opinion is determined more by technical implementation than by subjective judgment.

An audit report that objectively reflects the audit results demonstrates that the auditor maintains integrity in conveying conclusions. This objectivity is a key element in forming a credible opinion. Therefore, even when judgment is exercised, the opinion remains based on the factual audit results and is not influenced by personal judgment.

Although the auditor demonstrates consistency in performing audit procedures efficiently and in accordance with objectives, this does not directly affect the opinion issued. The opinion is determined more by the execution of procedures and the collection of sufficient evidence, rather than by subjective judgment. This demonstrates that the audit opinion relies on objective, measurable factors.

Audit judgment is indeed important in the audit process, but research shows that it has no impact on the final opinion. The audit opinion is more influenced by the implementation of appropriate procedures and strong evidence than by the auditor's personal judgment. Therefore, judgment plays a more supporting role than a determining factor in the opinion-making process.

Audit judgment is the auditor's professional decision-making process in assessing audit evidence, risks, and the fairness of financial statements. This judgment is subjective and influenced by the auditor's experience, knowledge, and understanding of the audit context. While audit judgment is theoretically considered crucial, in practice, its direct impact on the audit opinion can vary depending on the procedures' structure and the standards applied.

The insignificant influence of audit judgment can be explained by the existence of quality control mechanisms and strict audit standards at public accounting firms. Auditors tend to follow standard guidelines and procedures that limit the scope for subjectivity in issuing opinions. This results in individual judgment not always being reflected in the final audit opinion.

Theoretically, audit judgment plays a role in assessing areas with high estimation or uncertainty, such as asset valuation or loss allowances. However, in Indonesian audit practice, audit opinion decisions are often based on the compilation of objective and standardized evidence. Therefore, auditor judgment serves more as an analytical tool than as a determinant of opinion.

Although audit judgment does not have a direct significant effect, audit experience can act as a moderating

variable, strengthening the quality of that judgment. Experienced auditors tend to have greater intuition and analytical acumen, which can influence the evaluation process even if it is not statistically reflected in the opinion. Thus, it is important to consider the interaction between judgment and experience to more comprehensively understand audit dynamics.

This finding aligns with research by Masfa'ani (2021) and Nurdiatama (2020), which also found that audit judgment had no significant influence on audit opinions. Both explained that while judgment is a crucial part of the audit process, the outcome is still influenced by factors such as oversight systems, time pressure, and standard audit procedures.

Glover's (2019) study explains that differences in perceptions between auditors and supervisors regarding the sufficiency of audit evidence can influence the consistency of audit judgment. This suggests that disparate standards for assessing audit evidence can hinder the influence of judgment on the opinion issued.

Meanwhile, Wedemeyer (2010) highlighted that regulatory pressures and compliance-oriented practices sometimes reduce the auditor's ability to exercise independent judgment. When auditors focus more on formalities than on critical reflection on substance, the influence of judgment on the audit opinion becomes significantly less visible.

In contrast, several studies, such as those by Florentina (2016) and Anwar (2018), found that audit judgment significantly influenced the issuance of audit opinions. This difference indicates that the influence of audit judgment can be contextual, depending on the audit environment, the quality of the evidence, and the role of judgment in each organization's decision-making system.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of testing and data analysis in this study, it can be concluded that Fair presentation has a significant effect on the issuance of an audit opinion, indicating that fair presentation of financial statements plays a crucial role in forming the auditor's opinion. Audit judgment does not significantly affect the issuance of an audit opinion, so the auditor's professional judgment in this model is not a primary determinant of the opinion-making process. Auditor experience has a significant effect on the issuance of an audit opinion, indicating that the greater the auditor's experience, the more likely the audit opinion will be accurate.

REFERENCES

1. Anwar. (2018). The Influence of Audit Judgment, Auditor Experience, and Auditor Ethics on the Provision of Audit Opinions at Public Accounting Firms (KAP) in Makassar. *AKMEN: Scientific Journal*, 15 (4): 574–582.
2. Arens, A. A. (2017). *Auditing and Assurance Services on an Integrated Approach*. United States of America: Pearson Education.
3. Boedihardjo, DC, & Ardini, L. (2024). Analysis of Audit Postulate Violations in PT Garuda Indonesia's Financial Statements in 2018. *Journal of Business Perspectives: ISSN. 2715-2596*.
4. Bouman, M. J., & Bradley, W. E. (1997). *Judgment and Decision Making, Part II: Expertise, Consensus and Accuracy*, *Behavioral Accounting Research: Foundation and Frontiers*. American Accounting Association: 89–123.
5. Chandrarin, G. (2017). *Quantitative Accounting Research Methods*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
6. Chukwu, G. J. (2019). Sufficiency and Appropriateness of Audit Evidence for Giving an Opinion on the True and Fair View of Financial Statements. *International Journal of Innovative Development and Policy Studies*, 7 (3): 36–43.
7. DeFond, M. L. (2018). The Primacy of Fair Presentation: Evidence from PCAOB Standards, Federal Legislation, and the Courts. *Accounting Horizons*, 32(3): 91–100.
8. Friana, H. (2019). The Garuda Financial Report Case: Evidence That an International Public Accounting Firm Can Be Breached. <https://tirto.id/kasus-lapkeu-garuda-bukti-kap-taraf-internasional-bisa-kebobolan-edil> (accessed November 14, 2024).
9. Garvey, A. M. (2021). Accurate and Fair Override: Accounting Expert Opinions, Explanations from Behavioral Theories, and Discussions for Sustainability Accounting. *Sustainability*, 13: 1–23.
10. Glover, S. M. (2019). Mind the Gap: Why Do Experts Have Differences of Opinion Regarding the Sufficiency of Audit Evidence Supporting Complex Fair Value Measurements?. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 36 (3): 1417–1460.
11. Harjono, H., Triatanto, B., & Supriadi, B. (2024). The Role of Entrepreneurial Orientation and Entrepreneurial Leadership of SMEs in the City of Surakarta, Indonesia. *Innovation Business Management and Accounting Journal*, 3(1), 70-78.
12. Haynes, C. M. (1998). The Relationship between Client Advocacy and Audit Experience: An Explanatory Analysis. *A Journal of Practice and Theory*, 17(2): 88–104.
13. Ibhadode, O. J. (2020). The Truism of the True and Fair View of the Auditor's Report. *International Accounting & Taxation Review*, 4(4): 17–31.
14. Jesika, ML (2015). Auditor Independence and Responsibility and Their Influence on Auditor Opinion (Case Study of Public Accounting Firms in

“The Influence of Fair Presentation and Audit Judgment on Audit Opinion Issuance by Public Accountants in Indonesia”

- South Jakarta). *Scientific Journal of Economic Bulletin*, 19 (3): 1-10.
15. Jusup, AH (2014). *Auditing (ISA-Based Auditing)*. Yogyakarta: YKPN School of Management Sciences.
 16. Knapp, M. C. (1985). Audit Conflict: An Empirical Study of the Perceived Ability of Auditors to Resist Management Pressure. *The Accounting Review*, 60(2): 202–211.
 17. Masfa'ani, R. (2021). The Effect of Audit Judgment, Time Budget Pressure, and Whistleblowing System on Red Flags and Audit Opinions. *Jurnal Ekonomika*, 8 (1): 759–778.
 18. Masrizal. (2010). The Influence of Audit Experience and Knowledge on Detecting Regional Losses (A Study of Teacher Inspectorate Auditors). *Journal of Accounting Review & Research*, 3 (2): 173–194.
 19. Nurdiatama, D. (2020). The Impact of Audit Judgment, Professional Skepticism, Audit Situation, and Audit Scope on Audit Opinion Provision. Accuracy: *Journal of Accounting and Financial Research*, 2 (3): 103-116.
 20. Nwaobia, A.N. (2016). The New Auditors' Reporting Standards and the Audit Expectation Gap. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research: Social & Management Sciences*, 2 (11): 118–132.
 21. Scott, W.R. (2015). *Financial Accounting Theory*. Toronto: Pearson Canada Inc.
 22. Shalimova, N. (2016). Qualitative Characteristics of the Auditor's Report. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 7 (4): 84–95.
 23. Siregar, WM (2019). The Influence of Audit Knowledge, Audit Document Complexity, and Auditor Experience on Audit Judgment at the West Aceh District Inspectorate Office. Lhokseumawe: Unimal Press.
 24. Suhendar. (2020). *Introduction to Accounting*. Indramayu: Adanu Abimata.
 25. Sularso, S., & Naim, A. (1999). Analysis of the Influence of Accountant Experience on Knowledge and Use of Intuition in Detecting Errors. *Journal of Accounting Research*: 154-172.
 26. Wedemeyer, P.D. (2010). A Discussion of Auditor Judgment as the Critical Component in Audit Quality – A Practitioner's Perspective. *International Journal of Disclosure and Governance*, 7 (4): 320–333.
 27. Yanwardhana, E. (2023). BPK Reports Jokowi, 80 Ministries/Institutions Receive WTP Opinions. <https://www.cnbcindonesia.com/news/20231208171729-4-495736/bpk-lapor-jokowi-80-kementerian-lembaga-dapat-opini-wtp> (accessed May 2, 2024).